

Microwave induced conformational change and aggregation of bovine β -lactoglobulin: An insight to non-thermal effect

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Recent studies comprise detailed comparative studies on thermal and microwave induced non-thermal conformational changes at the secondary and tertiary level of structure of β -lg to ensure the non-conventional heating can produce a non-thermal effect with analogous thermal range. Both the fluorescence studies and circular dichroic studies revealed the conformational changes of β -lg. SDS-PAGE study was carried out to identify the higher oligomer and the isocratic-HPLC was used to characterize the oligomer/aggregates. Morphology study with the help of FE-SEM technique was successful to identify the spherulitic oligomer formation during the aggregation pathway. In fact conformational change related neurodegenerative disorders such as amylopathies including Alzheimer's, Parkinsons and Creutzfeld-Jakob diseases could be envisioned in the view point of microwave induced conformational changes leading to the protein aggregation.

Keywords: β -Lactoglobuline, microwave, unfolding, aggregation, non-thermal.

Introduction

Microwaves are the electromagnetic radiations within the frequency range of 300 MHz to 300 GHz (wavelength 1–0.001 m). Generally, 2.45 GHz (12.2 cm wavelength) is the frequency allotted by an international commission for domestic and industrial ovens¹. Microwaves represent the non-ionising radiations which affects the molecular motions like ion migrations and/or dipole rotations. The absorption of microwaves causes a rapid increase in temperature of substrates under radiations. In case of solutions containing salts or strong acids and bases the energy can also be dissipated through ionic conduction results direct heating or overheating effect of the solvent in an inverted temperature profile rather than the conventional heating process². Microwaves being macroscopic (12.2 cm) there is a problem of positioning the sample inside a cavity. As the cavity is usually of similar dimensions to the wavelength of microwaves, standing waves will occur, resulting in an inhomogeneous field. Thus samples at different positions in the cavity will experience different field strengths and will heat at different rates. Cavity with a single standing wave should be used, with the sample posi-

tioned in the maximum field strength position. In domestic microwave ovens the problem of inhomogeneous heating is encountered either by tunable or mode stirrer (a rotating metal paddle that reflects the microwaves in different directions' to maintain the homogeneity in heating³).

The rapid demand of consumer products such as cellular phones, digital mobile communication/radar communication widely used in defense and also the economic food processing microwave ovens, are the central focus of radiation biology and altered biophysical aspects⁴. Therefore it becomes necessary to consider a comparative thermal and non-thermal effect so as to insight the microwave induced conformational change in the protein of interest and towards protein aggregation.

Some of the recent papers⁵ showed that microwave treatment augmented the kinetics of refolding of cold denatured β -lg. Change in conformation induced by microwave irradiation facilitated the chaperon binding capacity, was evidenced in the case of citrate synthates⁶. Laurence *et al.* proposed that pulsed microwave radiation triggers the stress response by altered conformation of protein⁷. A thirty fold increase in

bioassay kinetics was produced by microwave accelerated surface plasmon-coupled directional luminescence in a very smart time saving mode⁸. Microwave radiation also promoted formation of amyloid fibrils of bovine insulin⁹. A non-thermal heat shock response augmented the expression of small HSPs induced by microwaves^{10,11}. In contrast, X-ray diffraction studies on tetragonal lysozyme crystal shows hardly any non-thermal effects towards protein structural subunits apart from hydration dynamics of the globular protein¹².

Beta-lactoglobulin is a whey protein widely used in different food/beverage industries in the processed food stuffs, and it is a nice model to study the various biophysical parameters, ligand binding capacities, astringency, antiallergeny etc. Catalytic study of microwave assisted hydrolysis of β -lactoglobulin has also been performed for food technological concern¹³. Microwave irradiation altered the antigenic properties of bovine milk protein was reported¹⁴. Non-thermal effect exerted during microwave radiation probably produces a torsional stress in between solvent molecule and protein interacting upon the protein surface or produced by the collective intrinsic modes in protein because of excitation of rotational/vibrational energy level¹⁵. Thus change in local conformation can induce the protein molecule towards formation of large protein complex by covalent or non-covalent (hydrophobic/ionic) interactions.

In our present study, we have carried out a detail comparative thermal and microwave induced non-thermal conformational changes at the secondary and tertiary level of structure of β -lg to ensure the non-conventional heating can produce a non-thermal effect with analogous thermal range and indulging β -lg molecules to form disulfide-linked larger aggregates. Both the fluorescence studies and circular dichroic studies revealed the conformational changes of β -lg. SDS-PAGE study was carried out to identify the higher oligomers and the isocratic-HPLC was used to characterize the oligomers/aggregates. Morphology study with the help of FE-SEM technique was successful to identify the spherulitic oligomer formation during the aggregation pathway. In fact conformational change related neurodegenerative disorders such as amylopathies including Alzheimer's, Parkinsons and Creutzfeld-Jakob diseases^{16,17} could be envisioned in the view point of microwave induced conformational changes leading to the protein aggregation.

Experimental

Materials:

Beta-lactoglobulin was isolated and purified from fresh cows' milk following procedures described earlier^{18,19}. The final product was lyophilized and stored at 4°C. The purity of the protein was ascertained by SDS-PAGE, where a single band was observed. Concentration of β -lactoglobulin in solution was determined spectrophotometrically using an extinction coefficient of 0.96 mg⁻¹ mL⁻¹ cm⁻¹ at 280 nm. Sodium dihydrogen phosphate and disodium hydrogen phosphate (all AR grade) were purchased from Sisco Research Laboratory (Mumbai, India). Hydrochloric acid, ammonia, methanol, glycerol, urea, sodium acetate (anhydrous) and ammonium sulphate (all AR grade) were obtained from Merck (Mumbai, India). Acrylamide, bis-acrylamide, N,N,N,N'-tetramethylethylenediamine (TEMED), ammonium persulphate, SDS, bromophenol blue, coomassie blue, fluorescein diacetate-5-maleimide, Tris buffer, ANS and DTNB was purchased from Sigma Chemical Co. (St. Louis, MO, USA). All other chemicals/reagents and HPLC grade solvents were of the highest purity available.

Methods:

Development of time dependent thermogram of microwave radiation

We developed a thermogram in our laboratory to record the temperature rise in different time duration of microwave radiation at different power mode. A thermocouple as temperature sensor (K-type, measurement range: -50°C to 1300°C; resolution: 0.1 to 1°C; accuracy: $\pm(0.3\% \text{ rdg} + 1^\circ\text{C})$ for -50°C to 1000°C) with a flexible cord was inserted into the microwave oven through a small window and connected with a digital temperature displayer (DIGITAL THERMOMETER 305, Taiwan). During microwave treatment the terminal of the thermocouple was put into the sample/buffer solution and temperature was recorded as displayed on digital thermometer (Scheme 1, see 'Supporting Information' section).

Microwave irradiation of the protein samples

Protein samples were irradiated from a microwave oven at 2450 MHz at a desired power. During radiation a glass beaker containing 100 ml distilled water was placed centrally just below the sample holder to absorb any extra power/heat during irradiation. Sample solutions (1 ml) or buffer solutions (1 ml) were taken in the eppendroff of 2 ml capacities and

capped properly so as to avoid any loss of solvent due to evaporation during microwave treatments. Temperatures were checked with the thermocouple before and after irradiation. The temperature deflection in all cases was within the range of $\pm 1^\circ\text{C}$ of digital thermometer. Immediately after microwave radiation, samples were transferred into quartz cell for further studies.

Fluorescence study

Fluorescence measurements were carried out using spectrofluorometer with the protein concentration 0.1 mg/ml in 10 mM phosphate buffer, pH 7.5. Both intrinsic Tryptophan fluorescence and extrinsic ANS fluorescence were measured after various time duration of microwave treatment (10, 20, 30, 40, 50, 60 and up to 90 s) at a fixed power (P-40 or 320 Watt). Tryptophan fluorescence spectra were recorded with the excitation at 295 nm and scanning the emission wavelength from 305 nm to 420 nm. In case of ANS fluorescence, excitation wavelength was chosen at 370 nm and the emission wavelength was scanned from 420 to 550 nm keeping ANS concentration 50 μM in each aliquote. Fluorescence spectra were normalized and each data point were an average of triplicate measurements after irradiation of fresh sample from the same stock and correspondingly blank corrected.

Free thiol specific fluorescence assay

Free thiol (Cys121) of bovine β -lg was expected to be solvent exposed during microwave irradiation. As a consequence of enhanced reactivity an effort has been taken with a thiol sensitive fluorescence probe, fluorescein diacetate-5-maleimide, to trace the local hydrophobic environment of Cys 121, buried under the β -strand H and the small α -helix. Before and after microwave treatment, 10 μL of fluorescence maleimide-5-diacetate (FMD5) solution (10 mM in DMF; 50 μM) was added to the 2 mL β -lg solution (0.5 mg mL^{-1} ; 25 μM) immediately (M:P = 2:1). Finally, the emission spectra were recorded at room temperature within the wavelength range of 500–650 nm upon excitation at 495 nm. All the data points were an average of triplicate measurements and were blank corrected.

Retinol binding activity

The retinol binding activity of β -lg was measured by alteration in fluorescence intensities before and after microwave radiation. In the first set, emission intensities of retinol

(pre-bound to β -lg) were monitored after several time exposures in microwave irradiation at 480 nm. In second set, only β -lg solutions were microwave treated and allowed to cool down to room temperature, then ethanolic solutions of retinol were added to the β -lg and spectra recorded (molar ratio 1:1). Excitation wave length was set at 330 nm and emission spectra were recorded within the wavelength of 450 to 600 nm. All data points were an average of triplicate measurements and were blank corrected.

Circular dichroism study

All the far UV-CD and near UV-CD measurements were performed on a JASCO J-815 spectropolarimeter using a cylindrical cell of path length 1 mm. Solutions were made in 10 mM sodium phosphate buffer, pH 7.5. Typical instrumental parameters were used: band width 1.0 nm, sensitivity 50 mdeg (for far UV-CD) and 20 mdeg (for near UV-CD), time constant 2 s, step resolution 1 nm/data, scan speed 100 nm/min. Protein samples were subjected to microwave radiation at a fixed power (320 Watt) for varied time durations (10 s to 60 s) and immediately after irradiation, samples were transferred to cylindrical cell for scanning.

Polyacrylamide gel electrophoresis

Polyacrylamide gel electrophoresis without SDS and with SDS were performed at room temperature with native and microwave treated β -lg solutions (5 mg/ml) for checking the possibility of formation of any oligomer/aggregates using a pre-stained molecular weight marker (10–107 kDa molecular weight range, Fermentas, Canada) and also to verify whether they are linked covalently (di-sulfide bond) or non-covalently (hydrophobic interaction). The β -lg solutions were irradiated for 20, 40 and 60 s respectively and aliquots were arrested immediately in cold at -20°C till the experiment. Gels were stained with Coomassie Brilliant blue R 250 and destained until clear protein bands were appeared.

Characterization of oligomers by Isocratic HPLC

The partially aggregated sample was characterized using a high pressure liquid chromatography (HPLC) on a Protein-Pack 300SW Chromatography column (7.5 mm \times 300 mm) consisting a WatersTM 600 pump, a Waters 2487 Dual λ Absorbance detector and Waters 600 controller. A 50 μL (stock contain 5 mg/ml) of treated β -lg sample was diluted with 10 mM sodium phosphate buffer (pH 7.8) and was loaded and eluted with same buffer containing 50 mM NaCl (pH

7.8) at a flow rate of 0.5 ml/min. The aliquots used for HPLC were taken from the same stock used for electrophoresis study. A UV detector was used to check the peak through optical density at 280 nm.

Studies of the morphology of the oligomers/aggregates

Characterization of oligomers/aggregates were done with the high-resolution Field Emission Scanning Electron Microscope (FESEM, model no. JEOL JSM-6700 F) with a range of 0.5–30 kV with a lateral resolution in the range 1.2–2.2 nm on the glass substrate according to Kamilya *et al.*²⁰ with a little modification. Aliquots of microwave treated β -lg solution were sprayed over the glass slides and left for air drying at room temperature. This spray-drying process was repeated for twice to achieve a detectable amount of oligomers/aggregates and finally gold coated before scanning under electron microscope.

Results and discussion

Time dependent thermogram of microwave radiation

Thermograms of temperature distributions by the microwave radiations with varying time duration at different powers have been constructed (Fig. 1). Here only P-40 (320 Watt) curve showed a convenient range of temperature distribution pattern with respect to conventional thermal treatment

Fig. 1. Time dependent thermograph of microwave irradiated protein solution (aqueous phosphate buffer, pH 7.5) at different power mode: P-20, 160 Watt (black); P-40, 320 Watt (red); P-60, 480 Watt (green). Relative errors in recording temperature were within $\pm 1^\circ\text{C}$ to $\pm 2^\circ\text{C}$. All data points are the average of triplicate measurements.

(25°C to 90°C). Therefore we deliberately chose the power P-40 at 2450 MHz in radiation treatment in all experiments.

Fluorescence results

Wave lengths for emission maxima for both conventional heat treated and microwave treated protein solutions have been plotted against temperature (Fig. 2). In the case of conventional heating, it appears from the plot that the change in conformation of β -lg in the tertiary level of structure was not so significant up to the temperature range of 60°C but onwards there was a sharp rise in emission maxima tending to the complete solvent exposure of Trp19 residue of β -lg which shows a good agreement with the result of Bhattacharya *et al.*^{21,22}. Fluorescence emission patterns of microwave irradiated β -lg samples show the partial unfolding which started after 20 s of irradiation reaching the temperature 40 – 45°C and a drastic change in emission maxima observed after 40 s and 60 s of irradiation reaching the temperature 50 – 55°C and 70°C respectively with a large red shift of emission maxima and a rapid quenching of fluorescence intensity within the same temperature range (Inset, Fig. 2). Therefore indole ring of Trp19, which is solely responsible for β -lg intrinsic fluorescence, is exposed to the aqueous environment not just because of alteration in tertiary structure induced by ther-

Fig. 2. Comparative representation of conventional heat induced (black) and microwave induced (red) unfolding studies. Excitation wave length was set at 295 nm and emission wave-length within the range of 310–400 nm. Quenching of fluorescence intensity was monitored at 335 nm in both the cases (Inset). Duration of microwave exposures were 10–90 s.

mal effect, rather, microwave treatment foster some non-thermal effect which is manifested in solvent accessibility by Trp19 either by complete distortion of tertiary level of structure or by rapid penetration of surface bound water molecules due to excitation of rotational/vibrational energy levels of the integrated protein molecules at the frequency of intrinsic mode¹⁵. Thus microwave treatment showed a remarkable change in the micro-environment of Trp19 accompanied by a change in global conformation.

The comparative assessment between thermal and non-thermal effect subjected to the change in local conformation of β -lg structure, we also carried out the extrinsic fluorescence experiment using 8-aminophenyl-1-naphthalene sulfonate (ANS). Results obtained from the studies of refolding kinetics, it appears that ANS is better encapsulated in the hydrophobic calyx of β -lg due to microwave treatment than the conventional thermal effect, as evidenced from the blue shifted emission maxima (Fig. 3). A large blue shift (469–471 nm) was observed after refolding of microwave treated β -lg where as only 5 nm (579 nm) blue shift was evidenced in the refolding thermally treated β -lg²¹. Keeping in mind the heterogeneous binding possibility at below and above the isoelectric point of β -lg (pH ~5.1) contributed by the electrostatic and non electrostatic (hydrophobic) interactions²³ and also in varying ionic strength²⁴ it was remarkable that microwave

treated β -lg adopt an altered conformation so as to envelop ANS in a more hydrophobic environment at pH 7.5 which is above its isoelectric point where the charge neutrality of both the host and guest molecules (ANS and β -lg) is quite impossible. Therefore accessibility of deep hydrophobic environment of β -lg by ANS reveals an altered conformation induced non-thermally by microwave treatment and also explores the idea of better encapsulation technique in biopolymers.

Free thiol reactivity

It was clearly observed that gradual increase in fluorescence intensities at 520 nm signified the trigger in free thiol reactivity with a specific probe along with the duration of MW treatment (Fig. 4). A sharp jump in intensity during 50–60 s exposure, indicates the sudden exposure of buried -SH group which co-valently bind with the dye (usually participate into disulfide linking of dimeric and oligomeric intermediates). But previously treated β -lg solutions showed poor reactivity towards fluorescein diacetate-5-maleimide dye due to almost participation in disulfide linked dimer/oligomer formation. Slight increase in intensity can be attributed to the residual free thiol (-SH) activity or S-S disulfide exchange phenomenon. Therefore conformational change in local pockets of buried -SH group is evidenced by fluorescein diacetate-5-maleimide assay as well as role of free -SH in disulfide linked aggregates.

Fig. 3. Blue shift in fluorescence emission maxima of 8-aminophenyl-1-naphthalene sulfonate (ANS) bound to β -lg during refolding after MW irradiation. Excitation wave length was set at 370 nm and emission was collected within the range of 420–550 nm within 1-2 min time interval (red to cyan). Arrow indicates the blue-shift and rise in emission maxima. Black line stands for emission spectra of ANS- β -lg complex at room temperature (25°C).

Fig. 4. Bar diagram of fluorescence intensities of free thiol (-SH of Cys121) specific fluorescence maleimide-5-diacetate probe in presence of β -lg before (green) and after (red) microwave treatment in different time duration (0, 20, 40, 60 and 80 s respectively). Emission spectra were monitored at 520 nm after excitation at 495 nm at room temperature. All the data points were an average of triplicate measurements.

Retinol binding assay

Biological activity was measured by induced fluorescence studies of retinol binding by β -lg under microwave irradiation. It was observed that fluorescence intensities at 480 nm of retinol bound to β -lg slightly increased after 20 s of MW irradiation and followed by a monotonic decrease in intensity which signifies a partial loss of retinol binding possibility (Fig. 5). Nonetheless initial increase in binding activity could be attributed to the reorientation of retinol inside the hydrophobic calyx of β -lg upon microwave-induced agitation of promotional infusion. On the other hand, the second set of experiment showed a gradual decrease in fluorescence intensities when β -lg was previously irradiated for different time duration and followed by retinol addition. It was distinctly observable that previously microwave-treated β -lg, lost the spatial arrangement of the micro-environment inside the hydrophobic calyx which fails to regain even after cooling down to room temperature, ultimately lowering the retinol binding activity in a time dependant manner. Therefore prolonged irradiations possibly obstruct the retinol binding activity of β -lg.

Fig. 5. Bar diagram of fluorescence intensities of retinol bound to β -lg before (green) and after (red) microwave irradiation at different time interval (0, 20, 40, 60 and 80 s respectively). Emission spectra were monitored at 485 nm upon excitation at 330 nm at room temperature. All the data points were an average of triplicate measurements.

Circular dichroism study

The far UV-CD spectral pattern (Fig. 6a) of native and microwave treated β -lg showed initially no significant change in the ellipticity values at the wave length 215–216 nm and

222 nm corresponding for β -sheet and helix domain respectively. Increase in durations of radiation, the ellipticity values started to decrease and it was observed that most changes took place in the wave length regions 208–210 nm and 190–205 nm and 190 to 205 nm ranges. Thus far UV-CD spectra indicate that β -lg shows a tendency towards random coil structure during microwave treatment probably due to torsional stress on the peptide bonds of β -lg. Jhong *et al.*²⁵ and Lee *et al.*²⁶ reported similar changes during thermal treatment of β -lg. Vetri and Militello²⁷ also reported that β -lg adopt an altered conformation prior to form inter-molecular aggregates at 70–80°C. The near UV-CD spectra of native and microwave treated β -lg are shown in the Fig. 6b. A drastic change in aromatic moiety of the intact β -lg molecule was observed. The disappearance of the signals at 293 nm and 285 nm, mainly considered as a contribution of aromatic residues, supported the fact. Nonetheless, enhanced signals in the range of 260–290 nm provided the information of sudden exposure of buried thiol group (Cys121) as was observed in case of 20 s of irradiation (preliminary detection by DTNB assay, not shown here), followed by reorganization through disulfide linked aggregation within the same temperature range. Though a small signal at 269 nm, contributed by Phe, were also changed. Collectively, it became prominent that

Fig. 6a. Far UV-CD spectra of native and heat-treated β -lg immediately after microwave exposure for different time duration (10–70 s). One of the spectral lines corresponds to the β -lg solution stored for several hours in freezing condition immediately after microwave exposure for 60 s (brown). Concentration of β -lg solutions were 0.25 mg mL⁻¹ in phosphate buffered solution (pH 7.5) for far UV-CD study.

Fig. 6b. Near UV-CD spectra of native and heat-treated β -lg immediately after microwave exposure for different time duration (20–80 s). Concentration of β -lg solutions were 1.0 mg mL^{-1} in phosphate buffered solution (pH 7.5) for near UV-CD study.

disulfide linked aggregates adopt an altered hydrophobic environment into the core of β -lg structure that was even successfully sensed by ANS, an extrinsic fluorophore. Thus non-thermal effect was quite supportive enough so as to induce a feebly altered global conformation of β -lg along with secondary and tertiary structural perturbation.

SDS-PAGE

Gel electrophoresis study in denatured (SDS) and native condition (not shown) showed no difference in the band pattern after gel electrophoretic run and staining with coomassie blue (Fig. 7). The sharpness of the monomer β -lg band disappeared gradually with the distinct appearance of protein bands with high molecular weight with concomitant increase in time of microwave in both the SDS-PAGE and native PAGE. Distinctly it was evidenced that in case of SDS-PAGE, band patterns appeared in the high molecular weight range are due to formation of covalently linked (S-S linked) dimer/trimer/tetramer/octamers or large aggregates even in presence of SDS. Though possibility of hydrophobic clustered could not be over ruled in case of native gel.

HPLC characterization

HPLC-elution profiles of native and microwave treated β -lg are shown in Fig. 8. The profiles of irradiated β -lg in

Fig. 7. SDS-PAGE pattern of native (lane 1 and 7) and microwave treated β -lg within the time duration of 20 s (lane 2, 6); 40 s (lane 3, 5) and 60 s (lane 4) in phosphate buffered solution at pH 7.5.

Fig. 8. HPLC elution profile of microwave treated β -lg (2 mg mL^{-1}) solutions. Promotion of aggregate formation was monitored by optical density measurement at 280 nm after 20, 40 and 60 s of microwave exposure and was eluted in isocratic mode with phosphate buffer (10 mM, 50 mM NaCl, pH 7.8) at a flow rate of 0.5 ml/min.

Table 1. Characterization of native and microwave treated oligomers of β -Ig in the isocratic HPLC elution profile. Molecular weight (in kD) and Stoke's radius (in Å) of the eluted samples have also been presented correspondingly

Retention time (min)	Molecular weight (kD)	Stoke's radius (Å)	Characterization of oligomers
11.32	~35	26.57 27.1 ⁽³⁰⁾ 26.47±0.18 ⁽³¹⁾	Dimer
10.17	~47 (43.5)	29.52 30.2 ⁽³⁰⁾ 28.7±0.44 ⁽³¹⁾	Intermediates
9.37	~57	31.78	Trimer
8.54	~65 (66.3)	33.37 33.9 ⁽³⁰⁾ 33.5±0.52 ⁽³¹⁾	Oligomeric Intermediates
8.33	~74 (78)	35.01 35.58±0.56 ⁽³¹⁾	Tetramer
6.23	~126 (130)	42.48 42.96±0.70 ⁽³¹⁾	Heptamer/Octamer

different time duration showed that the absorbances of sharp peaks increased in short retention time (Table 1) with a concomitant decrease in β -Ig native monomer/dimer peaks. Gradual increase in duration of radiation augmented the formation of large aggregates along with the oligomeric intermediates with different R_t , molecular mass and Stoke's radii correspondingly. Similar observation have been reported in SDS-PAGE results and in also case of β -Ig in solid phase, subjected to gamma irradiation²⁸.

It is well known that elevated temperature enhance the activity of free SH group and helps to form S-S linked aggregates in the time dependent manner. But, here, we have successfully produced that microwave treatment not only enhanced the free SH activity, even, was able to form large macromolecular aggregates within a short period of time in a very systematic manner beyond the analogous conventional thermal exposure.

Morphology results

The morphological pattern, imaged (Fig. 9) under Field Emission Scanning Electron Microscope (FE-SEM), clearly shows that some spherical clusters of β -Ig aggregates were closely associated. FE-SEM images of these dehydrated samples with different magnification have been presented (Inset, Fig. 9). Dark shallow portion of the image represents the FE-SEM image of a bare glass slide to compare the sur-

Fig. 9. FE-SEM image of aggregation pattern of microwave treated (60 s) β -Ig on glass substance with different magnifications. Large molecular aggregates along with spherulitic clusters have been shown with 50–100 nm scale bar (Inset). Arrows in the image specify the filamentous and spherulitic form of aggregates of β -Ig that indicate the microwave induced heterogenic aggregation pattern.

face morphology while compared the surface pattern of aggregates. From these images, it is evident that there is a heterogeneous population of spherical clusters primarily with diameter of ~50–100 nm (presented in bar scale in the images). Similar kind of spherulites composed of amyloid fibrils have also been found in case of bovine insulin²⁹. Some

shrunken filamentous pattern was also noticeable in the plates which were probably the large molecular aggregates with a varying length of ~2–2.5 μ m range (which fails to penetrate into the resolving part of SDS-PAGE, Fig. 7) formed in the mid way of propagation of long chain and dried under vacuum chamber with accompanying spheroids.

Conclusions

In this work, it appears that conformational changes in the tertiary level of structures of β -lg were more pronounced in case of microwave treatment rather than conventional heat treatment as evidenced by intrinsic fluorescence studies. It was also shown that ANS was better encapsulated in the hydrophobic core of β -lg during refolding pathway. Free thiol (-SH) activity of Cys121 was enhanced with the increase of microwave irradiation time. This Cys121 participated in oligomer/aggregate formation by disulfide linkage as evidenced by SDS-PAGE and isocratic HPLC technique. Therefore microwave induced binding of thiol specific fluorescein diacetate-5-maleimide proves that the microenvironment of local hydrophobic pockets of free cysteine get perturbed due to radiation effect on β -lg. Retinol binding assay also shows that the partial loss of the hydrophobic cavity under microwave stress probably because of alteration and re-organization of the β -barrel that fails to fit the retinol in proper orientation. This causes a decrease of fluorescence intensity of retinol bound to β -lg. The gross secondary structure of β -lg remains unperturbed but a pronounced β -sheet structure formation occurs upon rapid cooling (from far UV-CD measurements). But the signals in near UV-CD were lost due to microwave irradiation. As a result, these non-native/native like intermediates were more prone to form irreversible aggregates along with the soluble oligomers having spherulitic patterns. Morphology studies of the isolated aggregates of microwave induced β -lg were characterized with the dimension of 50–100 nm.

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Supporting Information

Schematic presentation (Scheme 1) of preparation of microwave irradiation on experimental sample is attached as supporting information for better understanding of the experimental set up to carry out the experiment in analogous thermal range.

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